

FEATURES OF BIOELECTRICAL ACTIVITY OF THE BRAIN OF 13-16-YEAR OLD ADOLESCENTS UNDER HYPOXIA CONDITIONS

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Abstract. *The purpose of the work was to identify age-related features of the distribution of the index and amplitude of the main EEG rhythms in adolescents aged 13-16 years under hypoxic conditions.*

We examined 75 practically healthy adolescents aged 13-16 years. Registration of biopotentials of various areas of the cerebral cortex was carried out using an Epas electroencephalograph. Indicators of the body's oxygen regime were calculated by an expert system for assessing the body condition of healthy adolescents aged 13-16 years.

An analysis of the distribution features of the main potentials of the electroencephalogram in adolescents aged 13-16 years under normoxia conditions showed that in this age group the formation of an EEG characteristic of an adult organism has not yet occurred. In adolescent children, the amplitude of delta activity still remains maximum, but it is lower than in children and ranges from 30.75 ± 1.30 to $36.83 \pm 1.32 \mu V$. The amplitude of the theta rhythm also decreases and reaches $13.67 \pm 0.38 \mu V$ in the right parietal region. In the central region, its amplitude is $26.50 \pm 0.53 \mu V$.

Keywords: *adaptation to hypoxia, blood supply, bioelectrical activity, electroencephalography.*

Introduction. The issues of interdependence of the functional state of various lobes of the cerebral cortex and subcortical structures on blood supply and oxygen supply are of great importance not only for characterizing the level of brain development and its functional state in healthy adolescents, but also for assessing the clinical symptoms of various diseases, in the pathogenesis of which hypoxia plays an important role. The above determines the relevance of studies of the characteristics of the total bioelectrical activity of various areas of the cerebral cortex and its relationship with blood filling and oxygen supply in adolescents of early puberty and puberty.

Electroencephalography (EEG) is a universal method for recording the bioelectrical activity of the brain. Unlike other methods of brain research, electroencephalography allows us to show one of the main parameters of the nervous system - the property of rhythm, which reflects the coordination of the work of different brain structures. EEG records primary changes, i.e. bioelectric processes in nerve cells.

The researches by physiologists and neuropathologists have established that the development and growth of different parts of the nervous system do not occur simultaneously and reach a certain, stable state, characteristic of adults, in different periods of postnatal development.

Therefore, it became necessary to study the age-related characteristics of the bioelectrical activity of various areas of the brain to identify significant changes in the process of individual

development. Characteristics of the age-related characteristics of the bioelectrical activity of the brain in adolescents aged 13-16 years are especially important, since it is during puberty that a natural increase in excitability and functional mobility of the brain occurs.

As we grow older, the role of the cerebral cortex in the activity of the body becomes increasingly significant, higher nervous, mental activity, which develops intensively in early puberty, has an increasing influence on the functions of the body. The functions of the subcortical region with its vegetative centers improve and become increasingly subordinate to the cerebral cortex.

Despite numerous studies on the bioelectrical activity of the brain in adults, studies aimed at identifying age-related features of the distribution of the index and amplitude of the main EEG biorhythms in adolescents aged 13-16 years under normoxia and hypoxia are quite scarce. All this determined the relevance of this work.

The aim of the study was to identify age-related features of the distribution of the index and amplitude of the main EEG rhythms in adolescents aged 13-16 years under hypoxia.

Materials and methods of the study. We examined 75 practically healthy adolescents aged 13-16 years undergoing treatment at the 2-city children's surgical clinic. The recording of biopotentials of different areas of the cerebral cortex was performed on an Epas 29/40/44/64/128 Schwarzer electroencephalograph (Germany, 2007) with topographic display of the results in the form of histograms and maps (brain-mapping) in the right and left occipital (O1, O2), parietal (P3, P4), central (Cz), temporal (T3, T4) and frontal (F3, F4) lobes of the cerebral cortex. The examination included recording the so-called "background electroencephalogram" (or "resting electroencephalogram"), and recording the electroencephalogram during functional loads: eye opening and closing test, rhythmic light stimulation, hyperventilation test.

The state of the functional respiratory system was determined using the method of A.Z. Kolchinskaya: tidal volume (TV) and minute respiratory volume (MRV), respiratory rate (RR) - using the VEB MEDIZINNECHNIK volume meter (Germany, 2003), oxygen consumption - according to Douglas-Haldane, oxygen content in inhaled, exhaled and alveolar air - on the INSOVT gas analyzer, arterial pressure (AP) - according to the method of N.S. Korotkov, heart rate (HR) and arterial blood oxygen saturation (SaO₂) - on the Oxyshuttle pulse oximeter from Sensor-Medicus (USA), determination of minute blood volume - by calculation. The indicators of the body's oxygen regime were calculated by an expert system for assessing the state of the body of healthy adolescents aged 13-16 years.

Statistical processing of the results was carried out in accordance with the rules of mathematical statistics using the programs "Microsoft Excel" and "Statistica 6.0" for "Windows". When conducting parametric analysis, paired and unpaired Student's t-test was used.

Results and their discussion. Analysis of the distribution features of the main potentials of the electroencephalogram in adolescents aged 13-16 years under normoxia showed that this age group has not yet formed an EEG characteristic of an adult organism. In adolescents, the amplitude of delta activity remains maximum, but it is lower than in children and ranges from 30.75 ± 1.30 to 36.83 ± 1.32 μV .

The amplitude of theta rhythm also decreases and reaches 13.67 ± 0.38 μV in the right parietal region. In the central region, its amplitude is 26.50 ± 0.53 μV . As can be seen from the obtained results, the amplitude of slow-wave activity decreases with increasing age, but remains lower than the indicators of mature individuals (Table 1).

Table 1.

*Amplitude of EEG rhythms in adolescent children (13-16 years) under normoxia conditions
(M±m), n=75*

Отведения ЭЭГ	Амплитуда ритмов, мкВ			
	Альфа	Бета	Тета	Дельта
Fp1A1	11,58±0,61	7,42±0,38	14,67±0,58	36,33±1,51
Fp2A2	17,08±1,31	8,75±0,60	25,92±0,87	33,58±1,68
C3A1	14,00±0,51	7,00±0,30	18,17±1,13	31,75±1,60
C4A2	26,17±0,74	8,92±0,63	26,50±0,53	36,83±1,32
O1A1	16,67±0,62	7,75±0,33	14,58±1,26	30,75±1,30
O2A2	18,17±0,82	7,08±0,26	19,25±0,68	33,17±0,94
T3A1	13,75±0,64	6,75±0,30	13,67±0,38	32,83±1,59
T4A2	18,50±0,86	8,08±0,69	20,17±0,67	32,00±1,22

In adolescents, the amplitude of the beta rhythm remains the smallest and reaches only $8.92 \pm 0.63 \mu\text{V}$ in the central areas. The amplitude of the alpha rhythm reaches $26.17 \pm 0.74 \mu\text{V}$ only in the central parts of the brain.

When studying the distribution of the EEG biopotential index, it was found that in adolescents aged 13-16, the alpha rhythm does not yet dominate the EEG; the index of the slowest activity (delta rhythm) is the highest compared to the indices of other rhythms.

Analysis of the distribution of EEG rhythms in individual lobes of the cerebral cortex of adolescents aged 13-16 indicates that in the frontal lobes of the cortex, slow-wave activity - delta and theta rhythms - occupy a dominant place. The sum of the indices of fast oscillations - alpha and beta rhythms in the left frontal lobe is no more than 21%, and its ratio to the sum of the indices of slow oscillations - delta and theta rhythms in the left frontal lobe is only 24%, in the right frontal lobe the sum of the indices of alpha and beta rhythms is 19%, and its ratio to the sum of the indices of slow activity does not exceed 23%.

In the temporal lobes, the index of delta activity, as in the frontal lobes, is high (about 63%), and the theta rhythm is 5-6% lower. The distribution of the delta rhythm in both temporal lobes is the same.

The alpha rhythm in the temporal lobes takes up only 14% of the total bioelectrical activity, the index of beta activity does not exceed 6.5%. The EEG shows some asymmetry in the ratio of fast and slow activity in the left and right lobes. In the left, the ratio of the sum of the alpha and beta rhythm indices to the sum of the delta and theta activity indices is 27%, in the right - 26%.

The increase in the ratio of fast and slow EEG rhythm indices occurs in the parietal lobes, where it is 54% and 57%. In the parietal lobes of the cortex, the alpha rhythm index increases compared to its values in the temporal lobes by 50% and more. Here, the asymmetry of the alpha rhythm distribution is manifested.

In the occipital lobes, despite the increase in the fast EEG index, the advantage remains with slow activity. The sum of the slow-wave oscillation indices is 61-63% of all EEG rhythms, but the ratio of the sum of the fast and slow wave indices is 57% in the left lobe, and - 67% in the right occipital lobe.

For this reason, in adolescents in early puberty, slow bioelectrical activity is predominant, and the alpha rhythm is not yet leading. The indices and amplitude of the alpha rhythm in different parts of the cerebral cortex in the early puberty period are lower, and the delta rhythm index is almost 2 times higher than in children.

The studies conducted revealed the dependence of the bioelectrical activity of the brain on the state of the functional respiratory system. The functional respiratory system provides the brain with the necessary amount of oxygen. The rate of oxygen supply to the alveoli, the rate of oxygen transport by arterial and venous blood, the degree of oxygen saturation and tension in arterial blood revealed in adolescents make it possible to provide the structures of the brain with oxygen adequate to its needs.

When the body of adolescents was exposed to a hypoxic mixture with an oxygen content of 14%, they developed subcompensated hypoxia, in which the damaging effect of local tissue hypoxia was already beginning to manifest itself. In the temporal lobes, there were also significant shifts in the alpha rhythm during hypoxia: in the left temporal lobe, the index increased by an average of 42%, and in the right temporal lobe, the increase reached an average of 82%.

As a result of the frontal lobe reactions to hypoxia, a more significant increase in the alpha rhythm index is also observed in the right half - from $13.14 \pm 1.18\%$ to $21.99 \pm 1.22\%$, i.e. by 67%, and to a lesser extent in the left frontal lobe - from $13.32 \pm 0.63\%$ to $16.92 \pm 1.12\%$, i.e. by 27%. This indicates that hypoxic exposure caused an asymmetric distribution of the alpha rhythm index within the studied areas of the cerebral cortex (Table 2).

Table 2.

EEG rhythm index in adolescents aged 13-16 years under hypoxic conditions ($M \pm m$), $n=75$

Отв- дения ЭЭГ	Индекс ритмов (%)			
	Альфа	Бета	Тета	Дельта
F3	22,24± 2,16	4,04± 0,33	19,64± 1,20	52,66± 2,49
F4	18,55± 2,10*	3,87± 0,41*	18,36± 1,67	58,99± 2,57
T3	23,39± 2,23	5,41± 0,65	18,73± 1,10	52,48± 2,33
T4	23,70± 2,41	4,21± 0,36*	14,21± 0,88*	57,87± 2,22*
Cz	22,97± 1,91	4,20± 0,45	20,50± 1,16	52,32± 2,27
P3	34,21± 3,01*	5,76± 0,59*	16,56± 1,05	43,48± 2,82*
P4	36,24± 2,55	6,19± 0,61	14,61± 0,71	43,82± 2,91
O1	44,35± 3,73*	5,79± 0,64*	12,07± 1,10*	37,79± 3,16*
O2	34,30± 3,00*	6,42± 0,50*	15,50± 0,69*	42,92± 3,02*

(*) – $p < 0.05$ in relation to normoxia.

As a result of the effect of reduced oxygen content in the inhaled air, the amplitude of the alpha rhythm in most leads also increased compared to the background. A more significant increase in amplitude is noted in the leads: Cz - by 22%, P3 - by 33% and P4 - by 14%.

As a result of hypoxic exposure, the average values of the beta oscillation indices increased to 6.20 ± 0.65 – $14.27 \pm 2.80\%$, by 25-53%. Moreover, the highest shift in the beta rhythm index towards an increase was recorded in the left and right occipital lobes, which averaged 14.27 ± 2.80 and $13.35 \pm 2.25\%$, respectively. In the frontal lobes of the cortex, in the left temporal and parietal lobes, small shifts in the beta rhythm index are observed ($p > 0.05$). In general, under the influence of hypoxia, the beta activity index tends to increase.

The increase in the theta rhythm index under the influence of a reduced O_2 content in the inhaled air deserves attention. The theta rhythm index under normal breathing conditions was within the range from 9.74 ± 1.001 to $8.40 \pm 1.29\%$. After hypoxia, the average values of the theta rhythm indices within the studied areas of the cortex increased on average to 15.76 ± 2.03 - $31.48 \pm 2.35\%$, which is 62-71% higher than the background values.

Higher values of the theta rhythm index were recorded in the frontal and temporal lobes of the cortex. In the left and right frontal lobes after hypoxia, the theta oscillation indices increased to $28.97 \pm 2.32\%$ and 31.48 ± 2.35 , respectively, which is 57-71% higher than the average background values.

Thus, hypoxic exposure leads to an increase in not only the index, but also the amplitude in all studied areas of the cortex. Moreover, higher values of the amplitudes and the theta rhythm index are characteristic of the frontal areas of the cortex.

It was found that the average values of the delta rhythm indices recorded in the studied lobes of the cortex during hypoxia are in the range of 29.22 ± 3.20 - $47.91 \pm 2.52\%$. In general, the delta oscillation index during hypoxia decreased by an average of 25-40% compared to the background. As a result of the hypoxic test, the delta rhythm amplitude also decreased by an average of 15-30%.

Conclusion. Thus, based on the conducted studies, the features of the distribution of the index and amplitude of bioelectrical activity of the brain of adolescents aged 13-16 years under normoxia and hypoxia were revealed. The prevalence of slow-wave activity of biopotentials (delta and theta rhythms) was found in adolescents aged 13-16 years; some increase in the index and amplitude of fast-wave activity is noted compared to children aged 8-12 years, but their values still remain lower than in adults. In adolescents of early puberty, with a lack of oxygen in the inhaled air, there is a decrease in slow-wave oscillations in the delta range rhythm and an increase in alpha, beta and theta activity. This indicates a peculiar reaction of the cerebral cortex of adolescents in connection with the functional hormonal changes inherent in the body during puberty.

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